

Parametric Control Design for Recovery of Fast Storage Systems after Virtual Inertia Provision

Kyriaki-Nefeli D. Malamaki, Chrysanthos Mitakos, Juan Manuel Mauricio, Charis S. Demoulias

Abstract—The increasing penetration of inertia-less Converter-Interfaced Distributed Renewable Energy Sources (CIDRES) and the gradual decommissioning of synchronous generators (SGs) jeopardizes the electric power systems stability. If CIDRES are properly controlled and equipped with Energy Storage Systems (ESS), they can provide ancillary services (AS) similarly to SGs. Namely, Fast ESS (FSS) can offer short-term AS, e.g., Virtual Inertia (VI). Despite the plethora of existing CIDRES/ESS control algorithms, little effort has been made to develop a proper Energy Recovery System (ERS) for FSS, to provide an almost ideal AS and to return its State of Charge (SoC) to a nominal steady state. An immediate SoC restoration of the FSS could cause further frequency deviations instead of properly restoring the frequency. Towards this, building upon previous work, this paper presents a parametric design for the control variables of a ERS considering a FSS. Specifically, a time delay is introduced between the VI provision and the SoC recovery. This delay and other control parameters are analytically formulated to allow the system operators decide user-defined parameters of the FSS ERS and avoid continuous frequency oscillations. The proposed control is validated via simulations in Simulink demonstrating its adequate performance.

Index Terms—ancillary services, energy storage systems, renewable energy sources, virtual inertia, voltage source converters

I. INTRODUCTION

During the past decade, there has been a considerable increase of electric power production from renewable energy sources (RES). Nevertheless, RES power plants (PP) are connected to the grid via inertia-less Voltage Source Converters (VSC). In the future, the synchronous generators (SGs) will be replaced by such RES PPs. Hence, the SGs inherent properties provided will disappear jeopardizing the stability and robustness of the electric grid. On the bright side, the advanced controllability of the VSCs has set a new paradigm in the Converter Interfaced Distributed RES (CIDRES) design philosophy. When the CIDRES are equipped with Energy Storage Systems (ESS), they can offer active-power related ancillary services (AS) without active power curtailment in a similar way to SGs, e.g. primary frequency regulation (PFR), virtual inertia (VI), the reduction of the injected active power fluctuations at the CIDRES terminals via Ramp Rate Limitation (RRL), etc. [1].

Various ESS technologies are commercially available. Based on the different power and energy requirements of each AS, different type of ESS should be selected: long-term AS with

high energy requirements, e.g., demand-response, and PFR, can be provided by battery ESS (BESS), while high power-to-energy ratio fast ESS (FSS), e.g., flywheels, [2] or supercapacitors (SCs), [3], can help mitigate short-term phenomena. In addition, there is a plethora of existing CIDRES/ESS control algorithms for PFR [4], [5], RRL, [6], [7], VI [8], [9], etc. Some of them also contain a State-Of-Charge (SoC) control after the AS provision, however, they mostly focus on the proper CIDRES control for the AS provision, while SoC control is not prioritized. As an example, for the provision of VI, many relevant studies assume an infinite DC bus and neglect the DC link dynamics, [10]–[12], while recent studies have shown that there exist a fundamental conflict between the DC-bus voltage control and IR provision, [13], [14] when including an actual ESS that is connected to the CIDRES DC bus via another converter. This is due to the fact that VI response leads to an energy release and, therefore, a SoC deviation from the reference value.

The reason for the above phenomenon is that VI response results in the release of energy, causing SoC to deviate from the reference value, [15]. Therefore, any SoC recovery approach relying on conventional droop control presents certain limitations depending on the values of the employed controller gains. Higher control gains will swiftly restore SoC to the reference value but at the expense of impacting the supplied VI. Conversely, smaller droops may not disrupt the VI provision, but they lead to a considerably longer SoC restoration time, [15].

The proper SoC restoration of the ESS after the VI provision is of particular importance, since an immediate SoC restoration could cause further deviations in the frequency stability, [16]. For this reason, it has been requested in the Nordic System to include a minimum time after the provision of fast frequency response until the start of recovery, [16]. Towards this direction, in [15] a new control strategy for the SoC recovery after the VI provision by a CIDRES involving a FSS was proposed where two main objectives were achieved: (a) Precise FSS energy release required for VI; (b) Fast and precise FSS energy control to recover the steady-state conditions after VI provision. A distinct characteristic of this method is that a time delay is introduced between the FSS energy release for the VI provision and the SoC recovery of the FSS. The effectiveness of the approach in [15] has been compared to a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller with both high and low gains, stressing out the limitations of such simplistic solutions in FSS Energy Recovery System (ERS).

In this paper an enhanced version of the ERS presented in [15] is described and evaluated in detail. Specifically, in this paper, the time delay (“dead-time”) between the VI provision

This research is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe project COCOON (GA 101120221).

K. - N. D. Malamaki, Chrysanthos Mitakos, and C. S. Demoulias are with the Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece. J. M. Mauricio is with Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Seville, Spain. *Corresponding Author K. - N. D. Malamaki: (email:kyriaki_nefeli@hotmail.com)*

Fig. 1. CIDRES/FSS Configuration with the VSG concept

and the SoC recovery of the FSS is correlated with the other control parameters in an analytical manner. This time delay is particularly important in terms of network stability, as it solves problems of consecutive under/over frequency phenomena with large Rate of Change of Frequency (RoCoFs) values, a significant advantage over other implementations and a desirable response from network regulations, [16]. The proposed approach actively determines the relationship of the "dead time" with the parameters of the control and sets new design perspectives for the operation of CIDRES/ESS, enabling them to provide VI and restore their SoC with a clear and configurable manner.

The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows: Section II provides a brief overview of the ERS control. Section III provides the analytical formulation for the determination of the "dead time". Section IV presents the system parameters, and the corresponding simulation setup, and discusses the results. Finally, Section V closes this study with its main findings, and proposes directions for further research.

II. BACKGROUND: CIDRES/FSS CONTROL

In this Section a brief overview of the control of the CIDRES is provided. Generally, it is assumed that the CIDRES is controlled as a Virtual Synchronous Generator (VSG) so as to provide VI. Any state-of-the-art VSG control [8], [10]–[12] can be applied. In addition, the SoC restoration of the FSS after the VI provision presented in [15] is briefly discussed.

The generic configuration is depicted in Fig. 1. In this configuration the FSS is connected to the DC link of the CIDRES VSC via a dedicated bidirectional DC/DC converter. In Fig. 1, p_s is the measured electrical power at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) of the CIDRES with the grid, p_m is the virtual mechanical power of the VSG, p_g is the measured power of the primary energy source, p_{FSS} is the FSS measured active power and p_l is the total system power losses. The power balance at the PCC is:

$$p_s = p_g - p_l + p_{FSS} \quad (1)$$

During a frequency event, the CIDRES should release power by the FSS stored energy based on the swing equation, [1]. The reference power p_{VI}^* that should be released by the FSS for VI is equal to:

$$p_{VI}^* = 2H \frac{df}{dt} \frac{S_b}{f} \quad (2)$$

where S_b is the nominal apparent power of the VSG, f is the grid frequency, $\frac{df}{dt}$ is the RoCoF and H is the inertia time constant in s . During steady-state conditions $p_{VI}^* = 0$ and in this case, the FSS should be able to recover its

SoC and then, maintain an almost constant SoC so as to be able to absorb/release energy for a subsequent event as well. Therefore, the FSS reference power p_{FSS}^* should be comprised of two terms:

$$p_{FSS}^* = \Delta p_{FSS}^* + p_{VI}^* \quad (3)$$

where p_{VI}^* is provided by (2) and Δp_{FSS}^* that is related to the FSS ERS. Consequently, based on the VSG concept and considering also the power balance, the virtual mechanical power p_m that is sent to the VSG is defined as:

$$p_m = p_s - p_{VI}^* = p_g - p_l + \Delta p_{FSS}^* \quad (4)$$

This study focuses on the definition of the term Δp_{FSS}^* related to the FSS ERS that differentiates from previous studies, [9], [13], [17] by adding the "dead-time" between the VI provision and the FSS ERS.

During a frequency event, the required p_{VI}^* and corresponding energy may deplete the FSS SoC. Thus, it is crucial to consider that the FSS has limited capacity. For this reason, it has been proposed in [15] to use two control blocks (illustrated in Fig. 2). The first one is based on a variable droop curve where the reference FSS energy is constantly modified according to an estimation of the FSS energy release that is used as an indicator of the VI provision. The second control block computes a power term which is used for SoC recovering purposes. These blocks allow to: (1) control the FSS energy so as to be as close as possible to the steady-state value E_0 and to avoid violating the FSS technical limits, $E_{min} < E < E_{max}$; (2) release the FSS energy for VI during a frequency event.

The FSS energy management system (EMS), [15] aims to calculate the FSS reference power p_{FSS}^* to provide VI as close as possible to the theoretical one given by (2) but considering also an optimal SoC recovery after any event (Δp_{FSS}^*). The yellow rectangle of Fig. 2 is the energy release control block that is further expanded in Fig. 3. The latter depicts an energy-power droop curve shown that defines p_{FSS}^* as a function of a variable reference energy E^* , i.e., $p_{FSS}^* = p_{FSS}^*(E, E^*)$. The points of the curve related to the FSS operational limits should not vary: (p_{FSS}^{max}, E_{min}) and (p_{FSS}^{max}, E_{max}) . The other points of the droop curve are modified according to the deviation of the reference FSS energy, E^* , with respect to its reference value $E_0 = \frac{1}{2}(E_{max} + E_{min})$:

$$\Delta E^* = E^* - E_0 \quad (5)$$

The parameter \hat{E} is the estimation of the FSS delivered energy, which is equal to E^* when the calculated E^* is within the FSS operational limits, E_{min} and E_{max} . On the contrary, if E^* is calculated to be outside (E_{min}, E_{max}) , then, \hat{E} is limited to E_{min} or E_{max} respectively. The estimation of the FSS energy release, \hat{E} , depends on p_{VI}^* given by (2), and the power required to restore the SoC value, Δp_{FSS}^* :

$$\frac{d\Delta \hat{E}}{dt} = p_{FSS}^* = p_{VI}^* + \Delta p_{FSS}^* \quad (6)$$

The part of the droop in Fig. 3 between $E_0 - \Delta E^*$ and $E_0 + \Delta E^*$ correspond to the FSS ERS and the term Δp_{FSS}^* :

$$\Delta p_{FSS}^* = \begin{cases} \lambda \cdot p_{FSS}^{max}, & \text{if } \Delta E^* < 0 \wedge \Delta E^* < \Delta E_r \\ -\lambda \cdot p_{FSS}^{max}, & \text{if } \Delta E^* > 0 \wedge \Delta E^* > \Delta E_r \\ 0, & \text{if } |E^* - E_0| < \text{tol.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Proposed FSS controller proposed in [15].

Fig. 3. Energy-Power Droop Curve, [15]

The parameter p_{FSS}^{max} is actually the DC/DC converter rated power and the maximum instantaneous power the FSS can provide. It could be prescribed by the System Operators (SOs) that the FSS does not recover its SoC with the rated power, but with a smaller power. For this reason, $\lambda \cdot p_{FSS}^{max}$ is the amount of ERS active power with $\lambda \leq 1$. This parameter is provided as input to the ERS control. ΔE^* is calculated with (5) and ΔE_r is a dynamic limit responsible for the virtual recovery energy deviation with respect E_0 . This new virtual variable follows the dynamics:

$$\frac{d\Delta E_r}{dt} = -K_m p_{VI}^* + \Delta p_{FSS}^* - K_r \Delta E_r \quad (8)$$

where K_m and K_r are parameters to be defined. Note that $K_m > 1$ in order to guarantee that ΔE_r is larger than $\Delta \hat{E}$. Once K_m is chosen, K_r can be defined to adjust the time constant of this first-order system (e.g. how fast the energy starts to recover). The virtual recovery energy is computed as:

$$E_r = \Delta E_r + E_0. \quad (9)$$

III. PARAMETRIC CONTROLLER DESIGN APPROACH

As presented in [15], the above control scheme exhibits commendable performance against other control approaches, such as a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller. The performance of the controller is depicted in Fig. 4 for RoCoF=0.5Hz/s, and $T_{VI} = 5s$ where the frequency is settled at $f_{Set} = 47.5Hz$. Note that the SOs usually would not let the frequency drop below 48Hz. The simulations have been conducted in Matlab/Simulink 2018b considering a SC as FSS with $C = 6F$. Other main parameters of the system are: VSC nominal power = 20kVA, the maximum power the

FSS can provide is $p_{FSS}^{max} = 2kW$, the SC operating voltage limits are 90-150V. Hence, $E_{min} = 67.5kJ$, $E_{max} = 24.3kJ$ and $E_0 = 45.9kJ$. The ERS power Δp_{FSS}^* depends on the parameter $\lambda = 0.1$, thus, $\Delta p_{FSS}^* = 200W$.

However, in [15] there has been a lack of design specifications for the controller parameters. In this section, the control parameters K_m and K_r will be correlated in an analytical manner with the physical parameters of the FSS (power, energy) as well as with some values that could be predefined by the SOs for "worst-case conditions", e.g., maximum duration of frequency event T_{VI} , and the maximum RoCoF, so that the FSS is properly sized to provide VI.

A. Mathematical Evaluation of the Dead-time

To facilitate this mathematical formulation, the power and energy response of the FSS during a frequency event are given in Fig. 4 (Middle) and (Bottom) where the various curves are split in parts. Before the event starts, the power values of the differential equation (6) are zero. The event starts at $t = t_0 = 0$, until it ends at T_{VI} (part $\overline{0A'}$), where the frequency reaches its nadir. At that time, the FSS should inject $p_{FSS}^* = p_{VI}^*$ given in (2). After the required VI energy is provided by the FSS at $t = T_{VI}$, the FSS should either recover its SoC or "wait" for a period and then start recovering its energy. At this point, two more time variables are set: ΔT_{DT} is the "dead-time", i.e., the duration under which the FSS remains inactive and $p_{FSS}^* = 0$, (part $\overline{A'B}$) and $T_{DT} = \Delta T_{DT} + T_{VI}$ is the time instant where the "dead-time" ends and the FSS starts to recover its energy. After $t = T_{DT}$ the SoC recovery starts and ends at $t = T_r$. During the period $T_r - T_{DT}$ the ERS power becomes equal to Δp_{FSS}^* (part $\overline{BC'}$). At $t = T_{Er}$, $\Delta E_r = 0$ and $E_r = E_0$ (part $\overline{C'D}$), thus, the FSS has returned to the steady-state SoC, E_0 . Based on the above sequence of events, the estimated FSS energy release variables of (6) are given by (10)-(11):

$$\frac{d\Delta \hat{E}}{dt} = \begin{cases} p_{VI}^*, & \text{if } 0 < t \leq T_{VI}, \text{ part } \overline{0A'} \\ 0, & \text{if } T_{VI} < t \leq T_{DT}, \text{ part } \overline{A'B} \\ \Delta p_{FSS}^*, & \text{if } T_{DT} < t \leq T_r, \text{ part } \overline{BC'} \\ 0, & \text{if } T_r < t \leq T_{Er}, \text{ part } \overline{C'D} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 4. Indicative response during a frequency event: (Top) Frequency; (Middle) FSS power; (Bottom) FSS Energy.

$$\Delta \hat{E} = \begin{cases} p_{VI}^* \cdot t, & \text{part } \overline{0A'} \\ p_{VI}^* \cdot T_{VI}, & \text{part } \overline{A'B} \\ -p_{VI}^* T_{VI} + \Delta p_{FSS}^* (t - T_{DT}), & \text{part } \overline{BC'} \\ -p_{VI}^* T_{VI} + \Delta p_{FSS}^* (T_r - T_{DT}), & \text{part } \overline{C'D} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Hence, actually, p_{VI}^* and Δp_{FSS}^* are complementary. Based on (10)-(11) and all the corresponding parts of Fig. 4- (Bottom), the first order differential (8) can be solved as:

$$\Delta E_r = \begin{cases} \frac{K_m p_{VI}^*}{K_r} (e^{-K_r t} - 1) \\ \frac{K_m p_{VI}^*}{K_r} (1 - e^{K_r T_{VI}}) e^{-K_r t} \\ \frac{\Delta p_{FSS}^*}{K_r} - \frac{(p_{VI}^* T_{VI} K_r + \Delta p_{FSS}^*)}{K_r} e^{K_r (T_{DT} - t)} \\ \frac{\Delta p_{FSS}^*}{K_r} e^{K_r (T_r - t)} - \frac{(p_{VI}^* T_{VI} K_r + \Delta p_{FSS}^*)}{K_r} e^{K_r (T_{DT} - t)} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

At $t = T_{DT}$, $E^* = E_r$, i.e., $\Delta E^* = \Delta E_r$. The maximum value of ΔE^* is expressed based on the FSS deviation from its steady state value E_0 :

$$\Delta E_{max}^* = |(E_{max} - E_0)| = |(E_{min} - E_0)| \quad (13)$$

The parameter T_{DT} can be found by setting $\Delta E_{max}^* = \Delta E_r$ by setting $t = T_{DT}$ for the part $\overline{A'B}$, hence:

$$p_{VI}^* T_{VI} = \frac{K_m p_{VI}^*}{K_r} (1 - e^{K_r T_{VI}}) e^{-K_r T_{DT}} \quad (14)$$

Based on the above, the duration of the "dead-time" is defined as a function of the duration of the frequency event

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for the FSS sizing and controller design

- Require:** RoCoF (SO), inertia constant H (SO), T_{VI} (SO), ΔT_{DT} , S_b (CIDRES Owner),
- 1: Decide p_{VI}^* via (2)
 - 2: Decide ΔE_{max}^* , i.e., the FSS energy considering also an additional cost limit of 10% with respect to the CIDRES total cost as in [7], the FSS energy can be determined, and in case of SCs - its capacitance and voltage limits.
 - 3: For given ΔE_{max}^* , ΔT_{DT} and other parameters considering $K_m > 1$, decide the control parameters K_m and K_r .
 - 4: Based on power system studies, decide ERS power do as not to cause subsequent frequency event.
 - 5: Distribute ERS power to the system FSS and several CIDRES and define λ for each VSG.

T_{VI} for which the VI should be provided and the control parameters given by:

$$\Delta T_{DT} = T_{DT} - T_{VI} = -\frac{\ln \left[\frac{-T_{VI} K_r}{K_m (1 - e^{K_r T_{VI}})} \right]}{K_r} - T_{VI} \quad (15)$$

The above solution is valid only when the event energy does not exceed the FSS limits, i.e. $E_{min} < \Delta \hat{E} + E_0 < E_{max}$. The maximum value of ΔT_{DT} is related with the maximum value of T_{VI} . The latter can be associated to the operational limits of the FSS as $T_{VI}^{max} = \Delta E_{max}^* / p_{VI}^*$.

Based on (14) the gain K_m can be provided as a function of the FSS physical parameters and the SOs specifications for RoCoF, T_{VI} , etc. and the gain K_r :

$$K_m = \frac{T_{VI} \cdot K_r \cdot e^{K_r (\Delta T_{DT} + T_{VI})}}{(1 - e^{K_r T_{VI}})} \quad (16)$$

Ideally, both controller parameters K_m and K_r should be defined by two equations but since there is only one equation (15) that combines all the involved variables, the controller designer could use (16) by setting different values to K_r and decide K_m . The simulation results of the following Section provides an insight on these values for a given FSS. The gain K_r affects directly the duration of the dead-time, in fact inversely proportionally, since it is in the denominator of the fraction. Since $K_r < 1$, the smaller the value given to this gain, the longer the ΔT_{DT} .

B. Proposed Sizing and Design

Based on previous studies, this section details the sizing and the controller design for a given FSS size, so that the FSS can provide VI. Assuming that the SO performs some power system studies, the ΔT_{DT} can be defined as well as the amount of ERS power so as not to cause any subsequent frequency event. **Algorithm 1** provides the steps considering parameters given by both the SO and the CIDRES owner.

IV. SIMULATIONS

A. System Under Study

The system under study regards the VSG control structure conceived in the frame of the H2020 project EASY-RES

Fig. 5. Overall Control Structure

(Unified VSG) along with the development of a prototype CIDRES DC/AC VSC [18] with a 3-level hierarchical control structure (CTRL1-CTRL3), depicted in Fig. 1. CTRL1 is the current control loop, CTRL2 is the DC-link voltage control loop and CTRL3 is the FSS voltage control loop. The first two loops apply a classic cascade control on the VSC DC-link voltage. All the details for CTRL1 and CTRL2 and different aspects about their performance and validation are provided in [13], [17]. CTRL3 is related to the AS provision (VI in this paper) and the ERS of the FSS. Hence, CTRL3 generates p_{FSS}^* . With respect to the power losses, p_l is replaced by a feed-forward losses compensation term \hat{p}_l due to the following reasons: during a frequency event there is a strong possibility that the FSS may fully charged or discharged, jeopardizing the DC-link dynamics/control, and the operation of the whole system. Towards this issue, based on various state-of-the-art control strategies, e.g., for static compensators [19], in [9], [13], [17] the feed-forward losses compensation term is calculated as:

$$\hat{p}_l = p_l \frac{1}{T_p s + 1} \quad (17)$$

Specifically, p_l are fed into a low-pass filter (LPF) before they are considered for the calculation of p_m and p_{FSS}^* . This action is performed so that the constant steady-state losses of the circuit are covered by the primary source, so that the FSS is responsible for handling the AS and does not provide power to cover the steady-state losses as well. Thus, this action prevents the loss of the DC-link control. The introduction of the LPF with $T_p > 5s$ as a time constant is explained in [9], [13], [17].

The simulations have been conducted in Matlab/Simulink 2018b considering the same parameters as in the previous Section for: C , VSC nominal power, p_{FSS}^{max} , SC operating limits, E_{min} , E_{max} , E_0 , $RoCoF = -0.5Hz/s$. For the parameters T_{VI} different values have been assumed, thus, the frequency is settled f_{Set} to different values depending on T_{VI} , i.e., for $T_{VI} = 2s$ $f_{Set} = 49Hz$, for $T_{VI} = 5s$ $f_{Set} = 47.5Hz$, for $T_{VI} = 10s$ $f_{Set} = 45Hz$. The ERS power Δp_{FSS}^* depends on the parameter λ , which takes several values during simulations.

B. Results

Firstly, the proposed analytical control design is compared against via simulations considering the detailed Simulink model. Specifically, for the given SC (ΔE_{max}^*), $RoCoF$, T_{VI} , K_m , K_r and λ , the resulting dead-time via simulations is compared to the result of (15). The parameter $\lambda = 0.1$

TABLE I
COMPARISON BETWEEN SIMULATIONS AND (15) FOR $T_{VI} = 2s$

		Dead-time, s		
K_r	K_m	Simulation	(15)	Error %
0.1	8	19.913	19.81	0.51
0.1	6	17.0345	16.93	0.59
0.1	4	12.98	12.88	0.77
0.1	2	6.0615	5.95	1.87
0.1	1.5	3.214	3.07	4.44
0.1	1.15	0.535	0.41	22.56
0.05	8	40.7	40.60	0.25
0.05	6	34.947	34.84	0.30
0.05	4	26.8345	26.73	0.37
0.05	2	12.9715	12.87	0.77
0.05	1.5	7.128	7.12	0.15
0.01	8	207.58	206.95	0.31
0.01	6	178.286	178.18	0.06
0.01	4	137.735	137.63	0.08
0.01	2	68.416	68.32	0.15
0.01	1.5	39.644	39.55	0.24
0.01	1.15	13.074	12.98	0.74

TABLE II
COMPARISON BETWEEN SIMULATIONS AND (15) FOR $T_{VI} = 5s$

		Dead-time, s		
K_r	K_m	Simulation	(15)	Error %
0.1	8	18.505	18.40	0.58
0.1	6	15.626	15.52	0.67
0.1	4	11.573	11.47	0.92
0.1	2	4.648	4.54	2.42
0.1	1.5	1.771	1.66	6.35
0.05	8	39.24	39.14	0.25
0.05	6	33.49	33.39	0.31
0.05	4	25.38	25.28	0.40
0.05	2	11.52	11.42	0.91
0.05	1.5	5.775	5.66	1.97
0.05	1.15	0.473	0.35	26.58
0.01	8	205.56	205.45	0.05
0.01	6	176.8	176.69	0.06
0.01	4	136.24	136.14	0.07
0.01	2	66.925	66.83	0.15
0.01	1.5	38.16	38.06	0.27
0.01	1.15	11.6	11.49	0.99

TABLE III
COMPARISON BETWEEN SIMULATIONS AND (15) FOR $T_{VI} = 10s$

		Dead-time, s		
K_r	K_m	Simulation	(15)	Error %
0.1	8	16.309	16.21	0.63
0.1	6	13.432	13.33	0.76
0.1	4	9.377	9.28	1.09
0.1	2	2.448	2.34	4.41
0.05	8	36.90	36.80	0.272
0.05	6	31.14	31.04	0.325
0.05	4	23.03	22.93	0.437
0.05	2	9.17	9.07	1.104
0.05	1.5	3.42	3.32	3.039
0.01	8	203.09	202.99	0.049
0.01	6	174.32	174.22	0.057
0.01	4	133.77	133.67	0.075
0.01	2	64.46	64.36	0.156
0.01	1.5	35.69	35.59	0.282
0.01	1.15	9.12	9.02	1.120

is constant together with SC and $RoCoF$, while the other parameters vary. The results are shown in Tables I-III. It is evident that the error between the simulations and (15) is less than 2% except in cases where K_m is very close to 1 compromising the stability of the control as evident by (8). This value needs to be $K_m > 1$ to achieve $\Delta E_r > \Delta \hat{E}$.

TABLE IV
EVALUATION OF ERS POWER VIA (15) FOR $T_{VI} = 5s$

$K_r = 0.01$					
λ	K_m	Dead-time s	λ	K_m	Dead-time s
0.2	8	205.554	0.05	8	205.56
0.2	6	176.785	0.05	6	176.8
0.2	4	136.239	0.05	4	136.24
0.2	2	66.924	0.05	2	66.925
0.2	1.5	38.156	0.05	1.5	38.16
0.2	1.15	11.622	0.05	1.15	11.6
$K_r = 0.1$					
λ	K_m	Dead-time s	λ	K_m	Dead-time s
0.2	8	18.515	0.05	8	18.505
0.2	6	15.636	0.05	6	15.626
0.2	4	11.586	0.05	4	11.573
0.2	2	4.642	0.05	2	4.648
0.2	1.5	1.759	0.05	1.5	1.771

In the second round of simulations, the effect of the parameter λ , i.e., the ERS power, is evaluated via simulations considering $T_{VI} = 5s$. The results are shown in Table IV for two values of λ , while the third value appears in Table II. As it can be observed, for given topology, RoCoF, T_{VI} and for given control parameters K_m and K_r , the value λ can take any value not affecting the provision of VI or the dead-time duration. Only the duration $T_{E_r} - T_r$ of the SoC recovery is affected. It is up to the SO then based on power system studies in how much time it will take to recover. This is a matter of further research.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces an enhanced version of the Energy Recovery System (ERS) previously presented in [15]. The primary focus of this enhancement centers on providing a parametric controller design based on system parameters and emphasizing the incorporation of a "dead-time" (time delay) between the release of energy from the FSS for VI and the recovery of SoC in the FSS. The controller design details take into account potential values supplied by System Operators to both FSS and CIDRES manufacturers. This approach actively establishes a correlation between the "dead time" and control parameters in an analytical fashion that introduces novel perspectives for CIDRES operation. This way, the CIDRES can contribute to the VI provision in a transparent and configurable manner, enhancing overall operation with network requirements. The introduced time delay can play a pivotal role in augmenting network stability, particularly in addressing issues related to consecutive under/over frequency events characterized by significant RoCoFs. This distinctive feature sets it apart from other implementations and ensures compliance with network regulations, resulting in a favorable and effective response. In future work, the proposed controller design can be incorporated in a CIDRES/FSS prototype and its performance can be experimentally validated. Finally, a future research direction is the evaluation of the proposed approach at power system level to define the appropriate values for RoCoF, frequency event duration, FSS size and ERS power considering specific power system topologies.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. S. Demoulias, *et al*, "Ancillary services offered by distributed renewable energy sources at the distribution grid level: An attempt at proper definition and quantification," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 20, 2020.
- [2] M. E. Amiryar and K. R. Pullen, "A review of flywheel energy storage system technologies and their applications," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 3, 2017.
- [3] M. Ceraolo, G. Lutzemberger, and D. Poli, "State-of-charge evaluation of supercapacitors," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 11, pp. 211–218, 2017.
- [4] D. Mejía-Giraldo, G. Velásquez-Gomez, N. Muñoz-Galeano, J. B. Cano-Quintero, and S. Lemos-Cano, "A bess sizing strategy for primary frequency regulation support of solar photovoltaic plants," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2019.
- [5] Q. Yan, Q. Bo, Y. Jingjie, M. Yunfei, and G. Bingqing, "Frequency control strategy of hybrid energy storage system for microgrid based on frequency hysteretic loop," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 103, pp. 328 – 332, 2016, renewable Energy Integration with Mini/Microgrid – Proceedings of REM2016.
- [6] D. Lamsal, V. Sreeram, Y. Mishra, and D. Kumar, "Smoothing control strategy of wind and photovoltaic output power fluctuation by considering the state of health of battery energy storage system," *IET Renew. Power Gener.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 578–586, 2019.
- [7] K. - N. D. Malamaki *et al*, "Ramp-rate limitation control of distributed renewable energy sources via supercapacitors," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 7581–7594, Nov.-Dec. 2022.
- [8] G. C. Kryonidis, K.-N. D. Malamaki, J. M. Mauricio, and C. S. Demoulias, "A new perspective on the synchronverter model," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 140, p. 108072, 2022.
- [9] G. C. Kryonidis, J. M. Mauricio, K.-N. D. Malamaki, M. Barragán-Villarejo, F. de Paula García-López, F. J. Matas-Díaz, J. M. Maza-Ortega, and C. S. Demoulias, "Use of ultracapacitor for provision of inertial response in virtual synchronous generator: Design and experimental validation," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 223, p. 109607, 2023.
- [10] T. Qoria, E. Rokrok, A. Bruyere, B. François, and X. Guillaud, "A pll-free grid-forming control with decoupled functionalities for high-power transmission system applications," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 197363–197378, 2020.
- [11] V. Natarajan and G. Weiss, "Synchronverters with better stability due to virtual inductors, virtual capacitors, and anti-windup," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 7, pp. 5994–6004, 2017.
- [12] S. Tan, H. Geng, and G. Yang, "Modeling framework of voltage-source converters based on equivalence with synchronous generator," *J. Mod. Power Syst. Clean Energy*, vol. 6, p. 1291–1305, 2018.
- [13] A. M. Gross *et al*, "Energy management in converter-interfaced renewable energy sources through ultracapacitors for provision of ancillary services," *Sustain. Energy, Grids Netw.*, vol. 32, p. 100911, 2022.
- [14] E. Rokrok, T. Qoria, A. Bruyere, B. Francois, and X. Guillaud, "Integration of a storage device to the DC bus of a grid-forming controlled HVDC interconnection," *Electr. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 212, p. 108601, 2022.
- [15] J. M. Mauricio, *et al*, "Short-term energy recovery control for virtual inertia provision by renewable energy sources," in *2021 IEEE 30th International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [16] ENTSO-E, "Technical Requirements for Fast Frequency Reserve Provision in the Nordic Synchronous Area – External document Version 1.1," <http://tinyurl.com/49m3kbb5>, Jan. 2021.
- [17] A. M. Gross, K.-N. Malamaki, M. Barragán-Villarejo, G. C. Kryonidis, F. J. Matas-Díaz, S. I. Gkavanoudis, J. M. Mauricio, J. M. Maza-Ortega, and C. S. Demoulias, "Energy management in converter-interfaced renewable energy sources through ultracapacitors for provision of ancillary services," in *2021 International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies (SEST)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [18] J. M. Mauricio, M. B. Villarejo, K.-N. D. Malamaki, and G. C. Kryonidis, "D2.5 final report on: the new electric and thermal dynamic modelling of dres/bess and dynamic functionalities," *H2020 EASY-RES Project Deliv.*, Aug. 2021.
- [19] A. K. Jain and A. Behal, *Modeling and Control of STATCOMs*. Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2015, pp. 339–369.